

Exposure to Traumatic Experience as a Correlate of Aggressive Behaviour among Internally Displaced Adolescents in Flood-Prone Areas of Anambra State

Okeke, Nkechi Uzochukwu (Ph.D)¹ & Anierobi, Elizabeth Ifeoma²

Department of Educational Foundations,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka
drnkechiokeke@gmail.com

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4055791>

Abstract

The study adopted a correlation survey design to determine the relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state. From a population of 3,112 internally displaced adolescents in 14 IDPs camp in Anambra state, 420 who manifest aggressive behaviours via administration of Buss and Perry aggression questionnaire (instrument) formed the sample for the study. Data were collected through questionnaire of 20 items structured to elicit information on the behavioural and emotional response of internally displaced adolescents to traumatic exposure. The instrument was validated by three experts in the field of education. Reliability of the instrument was determined using cronbach Alpha and an alpha coefficient of 0.81 was obtained. Research questions were answered using frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis was used for testing hypothesis 1, while hypothesis 2 was tested using t-test. Result revealed that internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state to a high extent experiences trauma. It also revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state. The researchers recommend social support from Government, families and non-governmental organizations which may help adolescent disaster victims manage feelings of aggression, anxiety, depression and loneliness among others.

Key words: Traumatic experience, aggressive behaviours, adolescents, internally displacement, flood, flood-prone areas.

Introduction

We all use the word trauma to mean a highly stressful event but the key to understanding traumatic events is that it refers to extreme stress that overwhelms a person's ability to cope. A traumatic experience creates psychological trauma when it overwhelms the individual's ability to cope, and leaves that person fearing death, annihilation, mutilation, or psychosis. The individual may feel emotionally, cognitively and physically overwhelmed. Traumatic events in

the field of psychology are most often conceptualized as life threatening and anxiety provoking experiences as noted by researchers like Birrell and Freyd (2017); Magee (2012).

It is the subjective experience of the objective events that constitutes the trauma. The more you believed you are endangered, the more traumatized you will be. Psychologically, the bottom line of trauma is overwhelming emotion and a feeling of utter helplessness. There may or may not be bodily injury, but psychological trauma is coupled with physiological upheaval that plays a leading role in the long-range effects.

Experiencing trauma can have a dramatic effect on our bodies and our minds. Traumatic experiences often involve a threat to life or safety, but any situation that leaves you feeling overwhelmed and isolated can result in trauma, even if it does not involve physical harm. It is not the objective circumstances that determine whether an event is traumatic, but your subjective emotional experience of the event. The more frightened and helpless you feel, the more likely you are to be traumatized.

Trauma experienced by adolescents is a pervasive and serious public health issue that requires a coordinated response from health and mental health providers. Traumatic experiences can include witnessing or experiencing physical, sexual and emotional abuse, bullying, terrorism, loss of a loved one, family and community violence, refugee and war experiences, natural disasters (example flooding, earthquake among others), living with a family member whose care giving ability is impaired; and having a life- threatening injury or illness.

Community conflicts and natural disasters often cause large scale displacement of people due to destruction of homes and environment, religious and political persecution or economic necessity (Eme, 2016). Kofi Annan, Former United Nations Secretary General, noted that internal displacement is the great tragedy of our time. The internally displaced people are among the most vulnerable of the human family (internal-displacement.org). Displacement of people can be of a voluntary or forced nature. Internal displacement is rising across the world, particularly due to natural disasters and conflicts, but also related to socio-economic factors.

The concept of the “Internally displaced person” is critical. There are varying definitions but the most acceptable is that proffered by United Nations Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement (1998) who assert that internally displaced persons (IDPs) are persons or groups of persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular as a result of or in order to avoid the effects of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights or natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized state border.

While the United Nations Guiding Principles on internal displacement are not legally binding, their authority has been recognized globally, particularly as they draw from international humanitarian and human rights law. The African Union in particular has codified the United Nations Guiding Principles on internal displacement with the 2009 convention for the protection and assistance of internally displaced persons in Africa.

Olanrewaju, Olanrewaju, Omotoso, Alabi, Amoo, Lomomeke and Ajayi (2019) opined that internal displacement is one of the greatest tragedies of our time and internally displaced persons (IDPs) are among the most vulnerable of the human family. This is because the intensity

of internal displacement arising from different factors, which include violent conflicts, man-made and natural disasters, has become a global problem. In fact, in the past few years, reports of internal displacement have increased around the world, bringing about a change from large-scale refugee flows to amplified internal displacement.

In the context of this work, internal displacement refers to the forced movement of people within the country they live in. In Anambra state, thousands of people are forced to flee their homes or places of habitual residence each year for some reasons which include: inter-community conflict such as : Umuleri/Umuoba Anam dispute, Aguleri/Umuleri dispute, Ebenebe/Oba-Ofemili dispute among others, natural disaster example flood such as 2012, 2013 and 2018 flood in Aguleri and Umuleri in Anambra east Local Government areas, Awka north, Awka south, Ogbaru, Ekwusigo among others, violation of human rights, and even government example while some government are responsible for generating displacement for genuine reasons (development purposes example in event of road, bridge and housing construction), other government-induced displacement result from bad governance and oppressive regimes.

A flood is an overflow of water that submerges land that is usually dry. The Center for Neighborhood Technology, Chicago noted that floods are the most common and widespread of all weather-related disasters. Flooding is an overflow of water onto land that is normally dry. Floods can happen during heavy rains, when ocean waves come on shore, when snow melts quickly, or when dams or levees break. Damaging flooding may happen with only a few inches of water, or it may cover a house to the rooftop. Floods can occur within minutes or over a long period, and may last days, weeks, months etc.

In Anambra state flooding are caused by such factors like: overflow of water from water bodies such as river, lake, in which the water overtops or breaks levees, resulting in some of that water escaping its usual boundaries, an accumulation of rainwater on saturated ground in an areal flood, blockage of water channels with refuse and dumps among others.

Flood-prone area means any land area susceptible to being inundated by water from any source. Flood-prone area as opined by Evans and Evans (2007) is any land area acknowledged by a community as being susceptible to inundation by water from any source. Some part of Anambra state such as Anambra west, Anambra east, Ogbaru, Ihiala, Awka south, Awka north and Ekwusigo Local Government Areas are prone to flooding which cause damage to property and threaten the safety of citizens. A flooded place/environment is no longer a safe place and thus the existence of IPDs to accommodate displaced persons.

Anambra state government set up 28 IDP camps in 7 Local Government Areas to accommodate victims of flood. Information obtained from the executive secretary, Anambra State Emergency Management Agency (SEMA) reveal as follows: 6 IDP camps in Anambra west, 6 IDP camps in Anambra east, 4 IDP camps in Awka north, 4 IDP camps in Ogbaru, 3 IDP camps in Ihiala, 3 IDP camps in Awka south and 2 IDP camps in Ekwusigo.

When people abandon their homes, it is most often because not doing so would pose a serious threat to their safety. Flight is their only way to escape violence or disaster and preserve their life or well being. In such circumstances, internal displacement is obviously the better

option, but it can have adverse effects on people's physical and mental health as well as significant and long-lasting effects on adolescent's behavioral and emotional development.

The internally displaced adolescent experiences a lot of trauma. Strasburger, Wilson and Jordan (2013) opined that adolescence is the period of turbulence, instability and a higher likelihood to take risks that may lead to aggressive behaviors. Strasburger et al further noted that adolescence can be characterized as a period of becoming more independent. Mawson, Best, Beckwith, Dingle and Lubman (2015) explained adolescence as a transitional stage of physical and psychological development that generally occurs during the period from puberty to legal adulthood. Adolescence is a stage of life in the development of an individual which is between childhood and adulthood occasioned by physical changes called puberty.

Sacks and Murphey (2018) observed that when adolescents are exposed to chronic stressful events, their development can be disrupted. Adolescents' who have experienced traumatic events are at risk of developing serious emotional disturbances. Over time, adolescents' may adopt negative coping strategies such as aggression/aggressive behaviours.

Aggressive behaviour as noted by Tolanda (2018) is a type of behaviour where people attempt to stand up for themselves or exert power over others in ways that are hostile and violate the rights of others. People who are on the receiving end of aggressive behaviour, usually feel dominated, embarrassed, guilty or shamed as a result of the situation. Aggressive behaviours are usually intentional and meant to hurt someone, either psychologically, or destroy someone's belongings. Supporting the above, Amber and Tim (2019) assert that aggressive behaviour can cause physical and emotional harm to others. It may range from verbal abuse to physical abuse. It can also involve harming personal property. Aggressive behaviour violates social boundaries. It can lead to breakdowns in ones relationships.

The researchers visit to some IDs camp in Anambra state and scheduled interview with some of the selected adolescents revealed that internal displacement interrupts adolescents' education and separates them from their familiar environment, teachers and classmates, sometimes for months or even years. When they are able to go back to school, whether in their community of origin, host area or in a camp, they have to make up for lost time while managing the stress and trauma associated with their displacement.

Disruption to education can harm the mental health of displaced adolescents, many of whom may already be traumatized by their experiences and heighten their psychosocial instability. It can affect social cohesion and increase gender inequalities, damaging social life in the short and long term. It can also reduce adolescents' potential earnings and livelihood opportunities as adults, creating a poverty trap that endures even after displacement. Review of literature shows that there is paucity of studies in the area of exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents. It is against this background that the researchers want to find out the relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state.

Statement of Problem

All over the world, flooding is one of the main natural hazards that cause tremendous damage and a great many casualties. Some parts of Anambra state are prone to flooding which cause damage to property and threaten the safety of citizens. These areas are particularly susceptible to flooding due to the characteristics of soil, slope, land use, blockage of water channels and weather patterns. A flooded place/environment is no longer a safe place and thus the existence of 28 IDP camps to accommodate displaced persons. Irrespective of the cause of displacement, the phenomenon can have significant and long-lasting effects on the adolescents' behavioural and emotional development. The concept of traumatic stress or psychological trauma has developed to explain how experiences like exposure to natural disaster such as flooding can impact upon adolescents. Consequently, the aim of this study is to examine the relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses stated in null form which include:

1. What is the level of trauma experienced by internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state?
2. To what extent do internally displaced male adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state differ from their female counterparts in exposure to trauma and aggressive behaviours?
3. There is no significant relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state.
4. Gender is not a significant factor in exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state.

Method

The research design adopted for this study was correlation survey design. Nworgu (2015) noted that this type of study seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. The two variables in the study are: Exposure to traumatic experience (independent variable) and aggressive behaviours of adolescents (dependent variable). Thus, the study aims to explore the relationship between adolescents exposure to traumatic experience with aggressive aspects through self-reporting/evaluation. Relationship connection between exposure to traumatic experience among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state and 4 dimensions of aggressive behaviours namely physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility were explored. The population of the study comprised all 3,112 internally displaced (ID) adolescents from the 28 IDP camps in Anambra state. The sample of the study stood at 420. In the sampling technique, stratified random sampling procedure was used. The stratification was based on local government areas (urban, semi-urban and rural) in Anambra state. In Anambra state, 28 IDP camps existed in 7 local government areas namely Anambra east, Anambra west, Awka north, Ogbaru, Ihiala, Awka south and Ekwusigo. Purposive random

sampling technique was employed in selecting 2 IDP camps from each local government area, giving a total of 14 IDP camps. Selection of adolescents was via administration of Buss and Perry (1992) aggression questionnaire, and only adolescents who manifest aggressive behaviours were used.

Three instruments were used for data collection. First, interview schedule with selected adults from the 14 IDP camps chosen for the study. The researchers visited each of the 14 IDP camps on different days and 10 adult displaced persons (5 males and 5 females) within the age range of 50-60 years were interviewed. It was unstructured interview schedule aimed at eliciting information from the adults on their observations/comments on the adolescents' behavioral and emotional reactions in the camp. However, information obtained from the interview schedule as well as review of related literatures helped the researchers in structuring the questionnaire used for the study. Secondly, Buss and Perry (1992) aggression questionnaire was used to assess the aggressive tendencies of the adolescents. The instrument consist of 29 items structured in a 5-point rating scale of extremely characteristic (5), somewhat characteristic (4), neither uncharacteristic (3), somewhat uncharacteristic (2) and extremely characteristic (1). Extremely characteristic response was used as indicator of an aggressive tendency. At the end of the test, 420 adolescents were chosen. Finally, a researcher-developed instrument titled "Exposure to Traumatic Experience Questionnaire" (ETEQ) was used for data collection. The instrument has 4 sections with 20 items to elicit information on the behavioral and emotional response of adolescents to traumatic exposure. The instrument was a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

The instrument was face and content validated by three experts from the department of Educational Foundations (2 in Educational Psychology and the other in Measurement and Evaluation) Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha with overall reliability coefficient of 0.81. Four trained research assistants were engaged for data collection.

Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation co-efficient was used in testing the null hypothesis 1, while null hypothesis 2 was tested using t-test.

Result

Table 1: Descriptive statistics on the level of trauma experienced by internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state.

Range of scores	Extent of trauma	Frequency	Percentage(%)
0-35	Low	95	22.6%
36-66	Moderate	107	25.5%
67-100	High	218	51.9%
Total		420	100%

Table 1 shows that 95 (22.6%) internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state had low traumatic experience, 107 representing 25.5% had moderate traumatic experience while 218 (51.9%) had high traumatic experience.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics on level of traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours by gender.

Gender	N	X	SD	Av.Mean	Remark
Female	278	48.11	10.76	47.64	High
Male	142	47.23	11.13	47.64	Low

Table 2 shows that internally displaced female adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state had higher mean 48.11, SD- 10.76 as compared to their male counterparts with a mean of 47.23 and SD- 11.13 who scored below the average mean. This means that internally displaced female adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state is to a great extent more traumatized and manifest aggressive behaviours than their male counterparts.

Table 3: Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Analysis of relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours.

Variable	X	SD	N	r	R ²
Exposure to traumatic experience.	27.01	10.60	420	0.71	0.50
Aggressive behaviours	19.64	3.323			

Result in table 3 above shows the correlation coefficient of the relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state. Results show that the correlation between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours was 0.71. This means there was a positive relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours. The coefficient of determination associated with 0.71 is 0.50.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of gender differences in exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviours.

Group	N	X	SD	Df	Cal.t	Crit.t	p.<0.05
Female	278	3.07	1.75	418	1.544	1.960	NS
Male	142	2.83	1.67				

Table 4 shows that at 0.05 percent level of significance and 418 degree of freedom, the calculated t = 1.544 is less than the critical t = 1.960. Therefore, null hypothesis 2 was accepted. It was concluded that gender is not a significant factor in exposure to traumatic experience and

aggressive behaviours among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state. Exposure to traumatic experience mean scores of internally displaced female adolescents ($x = 3.07$, $SD = 1.75$ and male ($x = 2.83$, $SD = 1.67$), $t(418) = 1.544$, $p < 0.05$. It means that both internally displaced male and female adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state were exposed to trauma and manifests aggressive behaviours.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that internally displaced adolescents in flood prone areas of Anambra state to a high extent experiences trauma. This agrees with the findings of Stacy, Allison, Berre and Jill (2011) that natural disasters such as flooding, earthquake among others exact heavy human and economic tolls. Stacy et al assert that it is not surprising that exposure to severe natural disasters is related to a variety of negative mental health outcomes because natural disasters often represent traumatic exposure. In fact exposure to severe natural disaster commonly involves what is often considered the hallmark of traumatic exposure. Again, the findings of the study aligns with Better Health Channel (2018) that a traumatic experience is any event in life that causes a threat to our safety and potentially places our life or lives of others at risk. As a result, a person experiences high levels of emotional, psychological and physical distress that temporarily disrupts their ability to function normally in day to day life. The findings of the study is also not different from that of Asim, Ahammed and Edwin (2019) that floods have considerable impact on mental health. They reported that physical and mental trauma on flooding has affected adolescents. Also in alignment with the findings of this research work is that of the American Psychological Association (2020) who noted that trauma is an emotional response to a terrible event like an accident, rape or natural disaster example flood. American Psychological Association further noted that immediately after the event, shock and denial is typical. Longer term reactions include unpredictable emotions like aggression/aggressive behaviours, flashbacks, strained relationships and even some physical symptoms like nausea or headaches. While these feelings are normal, some people have difficulty moving with their lives. The findings of the study showed that the level/extent of trauma and manifestation of aggressive behaviours by internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state varies with gender. Female adolescents' seems to experience trauma and exhibit aggression/aggressive acts than their male counterparts when exposed to natural disaster. Supporting this finding is the research work of Asim et al (2019) who noted that disaster-related problems manifestations such as aggression, anxiety, depression are more evident in female than male, thus gender is also a risk factor. They reported female vulnerability. Again, the Disaster Technical Assistance Center Supplemental Research in her September 2018 Bulletin, said gender appears to be one of the most important non-modifiable risk or protective factors when it comes to disaster reactions and recovery following exposure. Girls are significantly more likely than males to have major depressive episode or be affected by depression in general. They also observed that adolescents' girls have also been found after a natural disaster to be significantly more likely than boys of the same age range to experience trauma.

Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between exposure to traumatic experience and aggressive behaviors among internally displaced adolescents in flood-prone areas of Anambra state. This aligns with the findings of Grattan, Lara, and Niendam (2019) that those who have experienced trauma show higher rates of challenging symptoms and behaviors. Traumatic life events are associated with self-harming behaviors, aggression, increased substance use and impulsivity. Grattan et al said individuals with history of trauma were significantly more likely to report a history of aggression than those with no trauma history. They noted the most prevalent type of aggressive behavior within the trauma group was aggression towards others, and that trauma history is associated with more severe aggression. Again, Webb and Johnson (2018) noted an association between traumatic experience and aggression (both physical and verbal aggression) directed towards the young person's peers. Still supporting the findings of the study, Matta (2018) observed that the effects of trauma also can cause intense emotion, including extreme emotional fluctuations, anger and irritability/aggression. In line with the above, Newport Academy (2012) affirm that the emotional pain caused by trauma can lead to destructive behaviors. Adolescents who suffer from trauma have an inability to cope or process their emotions successfully. The findings of the study also agrees with that of Hardy and Vanden (2020) that traumatic events are inherently threatening and gives rise to difficult emotions. Man's nature is to automatically engage in strategies such as aggression/aggressive behaviours to survive trauma and manage these emotions. Hardy et al further noted that these strategies can become habitual ways of managing emotions, or emotional regulation, which can have unintended, unhelpful consequences.

Conclusion

Natural disasters such as flooding, earthquakes among others often cause large scale displacement of people due to destruction of homes/buildings. Internal displacement affects the social lives of displaced adolescents, their host communities and those they leave behind in many ways. Adolescents are the future of this nation and therefore it is imperative to preserve their health and well-being, especially in the face of disaster. Adolescents differ from adults based on varied psychological, cognitive and emotional developmental factors, making them more vulnerable to the damaging effects of natural disasters. In the aftermath of a natural disaster or traumatic event, adolescents may be affected by behavioural health conditions such as aggression.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend as follows:

1. Review of literature reveals that lack of access/limited education damage the social life of adolescents and encourages aggressive acts. On this note, the researchers recommend that the internally displaced camps set up by the government to accommodate the IDPs should be adequately and well furnished with facilities like schools, hospitals, markets among others. This to a great extent will make the IDPs feel at home and their social life will be enhanced thus reducing aggression/aggressive acts.

2. Social support from Government, families, non-governmental organizations may help adolescents disaster victims manage feelings of aggression, depression, anxiety, loneliness among others.
3. Natural disaster such as flooding results in internal displacement of persons. There is therefore urgent need for government and well meaning individuals/stake holders to make collaborative efforts through integrated flood management approach to provide long lasting measures to this disaster, so that it would not occur again in the nearest future.
4. Embarkment on sensitization campaign by bodies such as National Orientation Agency (NOA) and National Emergency and Maintenance Agency (NEMA) in order to create public awareness on the need to understand, prevent, prepare for and mitigate the likely effects of flooding.

REFERENCES

- Amber, E.G. & Tim, J. (2019). *Aggressive behavior/Definition and patient education- Healthline*. Retrieved from <https://www.healthline.com>health>.
- American Psychological Association (2020). *Trauma and shock*. Retrieved from <https://www.apa.org>topics>trauma>.
- Better Health Channel (2018). *Trauma and teenagers-common reaction*. Retrieved from <https://www.betterhealth.vic.gov.au>...>
- Birrel, P.J. & Freyd, J.J. (2017). *Reconstructing meaning after trauma*. Retrieved From <https://www.Sciencedirect.com>
- Buss, A.H. & Perry, M. (1992). *The buss-perry aggression questionnaire (aggression Instrument)*. Retrieved from en.m.wikipedia.org.
- Eme, T.O. (2016). A review of the health problems of the internally displaced persons in Africa. *Nigerian Post Graduate Medical Journal*, 23 (4) 161-171.
- Evans, D.L. & Evans, W.O. (2007). *The complete real estate encyclopedia*.Mcgraw-Hill Companies,Inc.
- Grattan, R.E., Lara, N. & Niendam, T.A. (2019). A history of trauma is associated with Aggression, depression, non-suicidal self-injury behavior and suicide ideation in First episode psychosis. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 8(7), 1082-1093.
- Hardy, A. & Vanden Berg, D. (2020). *A clinical introduction to Psychosis*. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com>
- Magee, L. (2012). *Encyclopedia of body image and human appearance*. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com>

- Matta, C. (2018). How trauma can affect your body and mind. Retrieved from <https://>
- Mawson, E., Best, D., Beckwith, M., Dingle, G.A. & Lubman, D.I. (2015). Social identity, social networks and recovery capital in emerging adulthood. Pmc Free Article, pubmed google scholar.
- Newport Academy (2012). Adolescents trauma and treatment. Retrieved from <https://www.newportacademy.com>
- Nworgu, B.G. (2015). Educational research: Basic issues and methodology (3rd edition). Nsukka: University Trust Publishers.
- Olanrewaju, F.O., Olanrewaju, A., Omotoso, F., Alabi, J.O., Amoo, E., Lamomeke, E. & Ajayi, A. (2019). Insurgency and the invisible displaced population in Nigeria: A Situational analysis. *SAGE Open* 9 (2).
- Sacks, V. & Murphy, D. (2018). The prevalence of adverse childhood experiences nationally by state and by race/ethnicity. *Child Trends publication* 2018-03. Retrieved from <https://www.childrens.org/publications>
- Stacy, O., Allison, S., Berre, B. & Jill, W. (2011). Challenges associated with childhood exposure to severe natural disasters. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Trauma* 4, Issue1, 52-68.
- Strasburger, V.C., Wilson, B.J. & Jordan, A.B. (2013). Children, adolescents and the Media (3rd edition). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Tolanda, W. (2018). Aggressive behaviors: Definition, types and signs. Retrieved from <https://www.study.com>
- United Nations Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement (1998). *UNHCR/Emergency Handbook*. Retrieved from <https://emergency.unhcr.org>
- Webb, R.E. & Johnson, D. (2018). The association between aggression, traumatic event exposure and post-traumatic stress disorder of looked after young people. *Scottish Journal of Residential Child Care*, 18(3).